

UMERC+OREC 2025 Conference

12-14 August | Corvallis, OR USA

Dynamic Load Monitoring and Analysis of Mooring Lines used by Wave Energy Converters

Pierre-Philippe Beaujean^a, Youssef Mohammed^a, Mohammed Abdellatef^a, Budi
Gunawan^b

^aFlorida Atlantic University, 777 Glades Rd, Boca Raton, Florida, 33317, USA

^bSandia National Laboratories, Albuquerque, New Mexico, USA

Abstract

Dynamic load monitoring and analysis of wave energy converter mooring lines was performed on a polyurethane-steel tension belt to evaluate its tensile behavior and assess the sensitivity of continuous monitoring using calibrated load cells. Both load cells showed consistent load trends, confirming a reliable and well-aligned test setup. The belt exhibited a smooth, progressive load response typical of viscoelastic materials. An exponential decay model was applied to quantify load attenuation along the belt, highlighting the impact of material damping and sensor placement on measured force. An alternate method was introduced to conduct tensile belt testing under controlled wave loading that is designed to simulate the higher loading conditions experienced offshore.

Keywords: wave energy converters; polyurethane-steel tension belt; mooring lines; dynamic load monitoring.

1. Introduction:

As wave energy converters (WECs) technology is becoming more mature, a new generation of units developed by private industry has emerged and is expected to become a common feature of the blue economy. The majority of these WECs is moored to the seafloor, and the ability to produce energy both efficiently and reliably is tied to the very design of the mooring mechanism. This paper explores several methods to determine experimentally the dynamic characteristics of a polyurethane-steel tension belt for rotary power take-offs (PTO) systems and wave energy converters. Polyurethane-steel tension belts are steel-cord-reinforced polyurethane belts that offer high longitudinal stiffness, minimal post-elongation, and high pitch accuracy that are crucial for synchronous drives. A prominent application concern is the unpredictable behavior and unknown life predictions of polyurethane belts when used for power transmission under winching elements and harsh underwater conditions [1]. The focus of the work presented is to compose a structural analysis of the belt under dynamic loading conditions. Continuously monitoring mooring load provides information on whether anchoring forces remain within safe thresholds, which help reduce the risk of structural failure during harsh sea conditions.

The authors initially developed a wireless apparatus, coined PADLOC, for the continuous monitoring and analysis of mooring lines using load cells, acquisition electronics and an underwater acoustic modem [2]. Every PADLOC unit could acquire, store and wirelessly transmit data to a remote user. Load cell data were both stored over the course

of months for post-processing and transmitted (in the form of statistical values or raw data at a reduced rate) wirelessly to a remote operator using the built-in underwater acoustic communication technology. The PADLOC technology thus allowed for the combined high-resolution data collection and transmission of information for continuous monitoring of the WEC mooring lines. As an outcome of this research, a total of eight PADLOC units were built (four of the first generation, and four upgraded units) [2].

Throughout the project, the experimental data indicated that a careful analysis of the mooring of operational and future moored WECs was necessary, for the purpose of predicting the mechanical robustness of the mooring and the efficiency of certain types of converters in capturing the wave energy. The experimental aspect of this analysis focuses on a specific part of the mooring, where belts are used to couple the wave-induced motion of the wave to the power takeoff units. These belts are attached to the mooring lines on one end, and to the power takeoff unit on the other end. To do so, a dual-axis load cell (Interface model LPXX-50MT-DB) is operated with the PADLOC unit in a controlled environment, using a Material Testing System (MTS) available in the Department of Ocean and Mechanical Engineering at Florida Atlantic University. This work goes in pairs with a model analysis to complete a comparative study between modeled results [3] and field results.

2. Methodology:

2.1. Load cell-based belt tensile testing performed on the MTS machine:

The test conducted was a tensile test performed under controlled laboratory conditions to evaluate the mechanical behavior of the 3100 μm Synchro-Power flat belt under uniform load increase and to assess the sensitivity of two data acquisition systems—PADLOC and the MTS machine—operating simultaneously. The Gates 3100 [μm] “Synchro-Power” Flat belt is made from high-strength thermoplastic polyurethane and imbedded steel chords [4], which is commonly used for heavy lifting and pulling applications. The belt sample dimensions were 250 [mm] length, 150 [mm] wide and 3 [mm] thick. The belt was securely clamped at both ends within the MTS machine, as illustrated in Figures 1 and 2, with the tensile load applied from the top. To ensure precise alignment, the belt was mounted with no angular offset (Pitch: 0° , Roll: 0°). The PADLOC is connected to the 500 [kN] Interface load cell (model LPXX-50MT-DB) mounted at the bottom end and connected to a computer to record load measurements (see Figure 2).

The extension rate is controlled by the MTS machine, and it is manually configured in the input section of the program. The extension rate was set to 0.000165 mm/s, and the test was conducted until a maximum load of 100 [kg-f] was reached. Elastomers show time-dependent strain [5] therefore, a slow extension rate (0.000165 mm/s) is used during tensile testing to ensure accurate characterization of the belt’s mechanical behavior under quasi-static conditions. A slow rate ensures that the viscoelastic composites like polyurethane-steel belts have time to respond to the applied load without introducing dynamic or rate-dependent effects like viscoelastic lag [6]. On the other hand, high extension rates may experience inertia causing noise, overshoot and inaccurate load readings that could mask true material responses. Especially when monitoring with two systems (like MTS and PADLOC), a slower rate ensures both systems can sample at appropriate resolution and Synchronize readings with minimal lag.

2.2. Tensile belt test under wave loading in controlled environment:

This experimental setup is designed to evaluate the mechanical response of the Synchro-power flat belt under simulated wave loading in a controlled lab environment. The setup is versatile, allowing for both MTS machine testing and water tank experimentation. The system features a vertically mounted water tank housing the belt setup that is clamped between a submerged buoy and a fixed base plate. The buoy, with a density of 16.0185 kg/m^3 and a net buoyant force of 1123.6 [N], introduces an upward buoyant force that mimics dynamic wave interactions. As illustrated in Figures 3(a) and 4, the belt is connected to the buoy through a mounting disk, while its lower end is secured to a base plate equipped with pins for optional deadweight loading. As shown by figure 5, The belt can be positioned at varying orientations— 0° , 45° , and 90° —to evaluate how different angles affect its performance under simulated wave conditions. The bottom plate. Figure 3(b), is set to handle over 1334.47 [N] downwards force to counteract the net buoyant force. The dual-axis 500 [kN] interface load cell is integrated in-line with the belt to precisely measure both vertical and lateral load components during testing. The load cell is interfaced with PADLOC data acquisition outside the tank, allowing real-time monitoring of tension fluctuations as hydrodynamic forces act on the system. The protective PVC cylinder is designed to eliminate drag acting on the belt. 90° brackets provide structural support and ensure alignment within the tank. This configuration enables repeatable testing of tensile belt

performance under controlled, wave-like conditions, making it highly suitable for offshore mooring or subsea tether system analysis.

Figure 1. MTS Belt Setup

Figure 2. MTS belt setup schematic

Figure 3. (a) CAD schematic of tensile belt test under wave loading in lab; (b) Bottom base plate.

Figure 4. CAD schematic of water tank testing lab.

Figure 5. (a) Schematic diagram of the belt tensile test orientated at 90 degrees (b) orientated at 0 degrees.

3. Load cell-based belt tensile results:

A sample of experimental results of data, acquired at a data sampling rate of 62 Hz in the MTS program and 0.62 Hz on the PADLOC, are shown in Figures 6 and 7. The Interface load cell data were initially sampled at 0.62 [Hz] while the MTS data were sampled at 62 [Hz]. The PADLOC interface data were then upsampled by a factor of 100 to retain the detail from the MTS system. Lastly, the x-axis was standardized (time and extension) so both datasets could be plotted and analyzed together.

Figure 6. Tensile test load vs. time results.

Figure 7. tensile test Load vs. Extension graph.

The difference in measured peak loads due to sensor position (top vs. bottom of the belt) can be explained mechanically; the PADLOC (bottom) measures the reactive transmitted load, which is a common viscoelastic material behavior [7]. A load transmission model (2) was developed that performs an axial force exponential attenuation through the belt in quasi-static conditions and estimates the expected load attenuation between the top (MTS) and bottom (sensor) using the exponential decay model for axial force transfer. The exponential attenuation model is inspired by the theoretical framework of the Capstan equation (1) that demonstrates how tension varies exponentially around a pulley [8]. In this work, the exponential nature of this concept is physically plausible in belt systems with the exponential decay of transmitted force over distance, and only the physical mechanism differs (friction vs material damping).

$$T_{out} = T_{in} \cdot e^{\mu\beta} \quad (1)$$

$$F_{sensor} = F_{MTS} \cdot e^{-\beta L} \tag{2}$$

$$F_{sensor} = F_{MTS} \cdot 0.5618 \tag{3}$$

Figure 8. Predicted PADLOC load measurements based on the force attenuation model (3).

In this case, $e^{-\beta L}$ represents force loss through material compliance and the underlying principle of exponential decay due to damping, rather than friction around a pulley. Both retain the same mathematical structure, reinforcing the legitimacy of the model. Thus, the experimental data acquired from the graphs above can be interpreted with this model, and the calculated decay constant (β) is -0.002306. Therefore, the produced force transmission model is equation 3. Which entails that the PADLOC sensor reads 56.2% of the MTS load measurements at peak, that is consistent with the calculated decay constant. The experimental results are then graphed in Figure 8, accounting for the attenuation across the belt, demonstrating the predicted PADLOC sensor load measurements at the bottom of the belt and it coincides with the raw experimental data.

4. Conclusion:

Both the MTS and Interface (Y-axis) load cells follow a similar trend, confirming consistency in the tensile testing setup. This test shows that the belt exhibits a smooth load increase over time. Furthermore, the maximum extension recorded in the test dataset was 0.07 [mm], indicating limited elongation under load. Together, these observations reinforce the conclusion that the belt behaves as a composite with limited range of elasticity capable of distributing tensile load without abrupt deformation or failure. However, for accurate load assessment in practical systems, sensor placement must be considered, and calibration models, such as the exponential decay correction, should be applied to reconcile differences between sensor readings. The sensitivity of the data acquisition method relies on the position of the sensor, as it was observed that there was a mismatch of 56.2% of load readings from both load measurement sensors.

Acknowledgements

Sandia National Laboratories is a multi-mission laboratory managed and operated by National Technology & Engineering Solutions of Sandia, LLC (NTESS), a wholly owned subsidiary of Honeywell International Inc., for the U.S. Department of Energy’s National Nuclear Security Administration (DOE/ NNSA) under contract DE-NA0003525. This written work is authored by an employee of NTESS. The employee, not NTESS, owns the right, title and interest in and to the written work and is responsible for its contents. Any subjective views or opinions that might be expressed in the written work do not necessarily represent the views of the U.S. Government. The publisher acknowledges that the U.S. Government retains a non-exclusive, paid-up, irrevocable, world-wide license to publish or reproduce the published form of this written work or allow others to do so, for U.S. Government purposes. The DOE will provide public access to results of federally sponsored research in accordance with the DOE Public Access Plan.

References

- [1] Nigel C. Kojimoto, Alex Hagnmüller, Phillip Gibson, and Budi Gunawan (2021) Cyclic bend over sheave performance of steel and aramid tension member belts for wave energy conversion. European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference 2021.
- [2] Pierre-Philippe Beaujean, Bryan Murray, Budi Gunawan, Frederick Driscoll (2022) Mooring Load Monitoring of a Wave Energy Converter using A Self-Synchronizing Underwater Acoustic Network. Ocean's 2022, Hampton Road, VA.
- [3] Abdellatef, M., Clark, J., Kojimoto, N., Gunawan, B. (2025) Wear of Wave Energy Converters (WECs) Mooring Lines. ASME Journal of Offshore Mechanics and Arctic Engineering, vol 147/2.
- [4] Gates Corporation. *Synchro-Power® Flat Belts: Engineering Data, Design Information, and Product Specifications*. Gates Corporation, 2022.
- [5] ASTM D412-16, *Standard Test Methods for Vulcanized Rubber and Thermoplastic Elastomers—Tension*, ASTM International, 2016.
- [6] J. Karger-Kocsis, T. Bárány, “Tensile Behavior of Thermoplastic Elastomers,” *Polymer Testing*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 648–656, 2009.
- [7] Tassara MF, Grigoriadis K, Mavros G. Empirical Models for the Viscoelastic Complex Modulus with an Application to Rubber Friction. *Applied Sciences*. 2021; 11(11):4831. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11114831>
- [8] M. Kutsenko and T. W. Theyson, “Finishes and treatments to control friction in textile fibers,” in *Friction in Textile Materials*, B. S. Gupta, Ed. Woodhead Publishing, 2008, pp. 386–418. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1533/9781845694722.2.386>.